

Popular Article

Moulting in Layer Birds

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Abstract

Moulting is a normal physiological process in which shedding and renewing of feathers occur in both sexes of bird. Generally wild birds moult before the beginning of cold weather and their migratory flight. Birds do not shed all the feathers at a time. Some feathers retain to body to regulate the body temperature. This moulting process is controlled by gonads and thyroid gland associated with drop in estrogen level there by decreasing rate of egg production. During moulting birds have a complete rest from laying. Partial/pre mature moulting is seen due to feed or water shortage, discontinuity of lightening, poor housing condition, improper temperature, disease condition *etc.*

Introduction

Feathers comprise 3-7% of the body weight of the poultry birds. Feathers contain approximately 85% protein. There are three principal kinds of feathers are present *i.e.*, contour, plumules and filoplumules. Contour feathers also known as body feather. They are large in size. Plumules are also called as downy feathers. It is present in chicks and below the body feathers in adult. Filo plumules are hair like appendages *i.e.*, degenerated feathers present after plucking. Moulting of feathers occur in very orderly manner that means head fathers first moult followed by neck, breast, body, wing, tail. The main wing feathers called remiges are divided into the primary and secondary flight feathers separated by the smaller axial feather. A poultry bird having ten numbers of primary feathers, one number of axial feather and fourteen numbers of secondary feathers. Primary feathers next to axial feather shed first followed by other primary feathers in sequential manner. After the complete shedding of primary feathers, secondary feathers shed. But this shedding is not a sequential manner. At last axial feather shed. For complete renewing of primary feather, it takes 6 weeks. Renewal of 2/3rd portion is completed in 1st three weeks and rest 1/3rd during last three weeks. Factors like body weight and physical condition of bird, length of light exposure, nutritional status of bird and environmental temperature and humidity affect the rate of moulting in broiler birds.

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Types of moulting

There are two types of moulting *i.e.*, natural moulting and induced moulting

Natural moulting

Usually natural moulting begins from March-April and should be completed by July when the egg production commences. There is no artificial interpretation done. It is slower and more erratic or uneven than induced moulting. It is due to mainly physical exhaustion and fatigue, completion of laying cycle, decrease in day length period.

Induced moulting

It is also known as forced moulting. Induced moulting is defined as the moulting process artificially induced by applying certain stress for certain duration in order to attain longer productivity period and some other advantages in commercial layer birds. In other words, it is a practice adopted by commercial layer birds to bring about a rapid moult so that all the birds come back into lay for second time at a certain time, usually in autumn. It is achieved by subjecting a flock to a programmed combination of mild environment and nutritional stress factor causing the birds to cease the laying and consequently moult (Berry, 2003). Entire moulting process completed in 6-8 weeks.

Purpose of moulting

Generally, the layer birds are reared up to 72 weeks and then liquidated. By this time the production of flock goes down and the replacement flock would be ready for housing. At that time there is lack of enough finance to buy a new batch of chick and wait up to sexual maturity and productivity. This happens due to two reasons *i.e.* Price of cull bird are non-remunerative (farm income and expenses do not match) and sudden decrease in egg price at April (due to summer), August and September (due to festival season). Therefore, in order to overcome this situation birds are allowed to undergo a sort of rest for some time by drastic reduction of feed then came back to production again results better production for a longer period. Induced moulting causes all hens in a flock out of production for a period of regression and rejuvenation of reproductive tract accompanied by loss and replacement of feathers. On the other hand, domestic chicken meant for high egg production do not enter through a complete moult until the laying period is prolonged. Thus, to speed up the process, a programme of forced moulting can be used. In some countries, rather than being slaughtered after completion of laying, the hens are force moulted to re-enter second and subsequent laying phase.

Mechanism of induced moulting

Advantages of induced moulting

- To minimize the cost to bring the flock into production.
- Recycling of hen for another period of production.
- Effective management of tool for extending flock performance and production.
- To obtain heavier, high quality and marketable eggs.
- Improves the liveability of the flock.
- When the current egg prices are low then losses will be fulfilled by higher price obtained during post moult.
- Increases the profitability of flock in their subsequent laying phase.
- Cash outlay for induced moulting of the flock is less than buying and growing a fresh batch.
- Moulted birds are more resistant to disease.
- Availability of empty houses.
- To avoid annual cost of replacing, pullets, vaccines, medicines and feed *etc.*
- Round the year egg production.

Types of induced moulting

Two cycle moulting programme

Involves one moulting and two egg production cycle. Hen moults for the 1st time at 10 months of egg production. Then birds back to production and sold at 24 months. It is most

commonly practiced in field condition.

Multiple cycles moulting programme

It involves two or more moulting and three or more egg production cycle. Hen moults for the 1st time at nine months of egg production. Then birds back to production and sold at 30 month and more. It is least common in field condition.

Factors of induced moulting

There are mainly three factors for induced moulting

Initiating moulting process

Moulting process can be initiated by fasting/starvation, limiting the critical nutrients like protein, Ca and Na, artificial light turned off or provide not more than 8 hour. As a result gradually egg production decreases and reaches to zero.

Resting the flock

Once the flock is out of production, this stage is maintained for 4-5 weeks by providing low protein and Ca.

Returning the flock into production

Providing layer diet and normal lightening the flock return into production. Usually 50% laying was reached within 2-3 week after removing forced moulting.

Methods of induced moulting

1. Conventional induced moulting (On again, off again programme)
2. Washington induced moulting programme (Low feed intake)
3. California induced moulting programme (No water restriction).
4. Chemical induced moulting programme (By feeding of chemicals like Zn, Low Ca).
5. Use of drug and other compounds.

1. Conventional induced moulting programme

It is an old and most popular method due to ease application, low cost and agreeable post moult performance. During experiment, first grade the birds and cull the weak and lame birds. One week prior to this programme deworm the flock. Four days after deworming vaccinate the flock against Newcastle disease and infectious bursal disease. Give three days 24 hrs. light before starting the programme. Weigh the selected birds on day 1 morning and record it. On day 10, weigh birds and check for the body weight reduction if it is not reduced a desired level then continue fasting. Body weight was reduced 23-25% during feed restriction. Most flock will reach zero

production by 6th or 7th day after feed restriction. Flock will back in production 5 weeks after restriction and up to 50% production in 7th week and peak at 9th week. Repeat lasota vaccine after the birds are back on full feed condition. The normal management practices are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Normal management practices during conventional induced moulting programme

Days	Feed	Water	Light
1.	None	None	8 hr
2.	None	None	8 hr
3.	45g/hen	Water	8 hr
4.	None	None	8 hr
5.	45g/hen	Water	8 hr
6.	None	None	8 hr
7.	45g/hen	Water	8 hr
8.	None	None	8 hr
9.	45g/hen	Water	8 hr
10 -60 day	Restricted feeding about 75% of full feed intake	Water	8 hr
61 days onward	Full fed layer ration	Water	14-16 hr

2. Washington induced moulting programme

Fasting methods is not practised in most of countries because of the welfare of the flock. This fasting/starvation are banned in India now. In such cases, the producer must follow a feeding programme in which egg production drops to zero without following starvation or fasting method. This method includes full or limited feeding of low protein or low nutrient diet, low calcium and phosphorus level in the diet.

3. Chemical induced moulting programme

In this method, about 20 g zinc per kg in layer diet (25 kg of zinc oxide per ton feed) is

used for a period of 5 days along with reduced photoperiod. Then the birds are provided 50 mg Zn/kg layer feed and increased light period upto 14 hours. During this programme, hens will consume < 10% normal amount of feed and will lose from 250 to 340 g of their original weight within the first 7 to 10 days (Mosaad *et al.*, 2016). On 5th day of this programme egg production reaches to zero. When this Zn programme is withdrawn automatically birds will come back into production within 7 days.

4. Use of drugs and other compounds

Compounds like methalibure, enheptin, progesterone, chloromadidone, aluminium and iodine show moulting effect when fed to birds at a particular concentration (Biggs *et al.*, 2005).

Nutritional strategies for induced moulting in layers

- Induce moult by providing low density diet (Grape pomace, soyabean hulls and whole grain barley).
- Feeding of low nutrient rations such as alfalfa in combination with 10%-layer ration can be effective substitute for feed removal with increased profitability.
- Wheat middlings is also used to induce moulting.
- Inclusion of 20% guar meal in layer ration successfully induces moulting and increases the resistance of hens against *Salmonella* infection.
- When excess zinc and aluminium salt contents in diet are given moulting induces.

Conclusion

Induced moulting not only judges and selects the superior bird but also improves the productivity and performance of the layer birds.

References

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